

A Cost-Effective Method to Measure Delayed Deformations of Building Materials

Ahmad Fathi¹, João M. Pereira¹, Graça Vasconcelos¹ and Miguel Azenha¹

¹ University of Minho, ISISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães 4800-058, Portugal
a.fathi@civil.uminho.pt

Abstract. Characterization of deformation related properties like creep, moisture expansion, drying shrinkage, and others, usually require a high number of specimens and long-term tests. Traditional measuring methods, such as LVDTs or Strain Gauges, end up being expensive, considering the initial cost, the time they are allocated to the experimental campaign, and the required data acquisition systems. This research proposes an innovative cost-effective solution to measure strains on building material using microscope scale images. The main features of the method are: a) cost-effective, b) appropriate for long-term tests, c) possibility of using with high number of specimens, d) good precision ($<3\mu\text{m}$), and e) open source. The development is being described into two stages including methodological aspects and validation which are discussed in this work. The developed method is based on a sliding ruler that is connected to the specimen. The ruler has two parts (one fixed and one movable), and their relative movement, as consequence of the deformation, is monitored with indicators. Using a USB microscope to capture sequential images, it is possible to determine the evolution of the deformation using artificial vision algorithms. This methodology was validated with traditional measurement methods.

Keywords: cost-effective, delayed deformations, construction materials, image processing, open-source.

1 Introduction

Strains resulting from delayed deformations, namely creep, drying shrinkage, and moisture expansion, of construction material can cause a variety of structural defects in buildings. Dimensional variations can result in changes in the magnitude and direction of the forces [1]; strength and stiffness reductions [2] can be caused by micro-cracks around the aggregates [3] or cracks in the structure [4].

Investigation of the delayed deformations requires large experimental campaigns considering the influential factors. These experimental campaigns usually require a large number of specimens. Considering such large experimental campaigns, the required investment in terms of measuring equipment and data acquisition systems is quite relevant. Having said this, the objective of this work is to develop an innovative measuring methodology to study delayed deformations of construction materials.

This new measuring methodology will use microscopic scale images and the overall method has been developed considering some features: a) applicable to long-term tests with a high number of specimens; b) cost-effective; c) high precision ($< 3\mu\text{m}$); d) open source. The procedure is being divided into two stages including methodological aspects and verification as described in the following subsections.

2 Methodological Aspects

The proposed measurement system consists of a microscope with a stand, a sliding ruler, and an indicator. The sliding ruler is attached to the specimen with the fixation points defining the location where the deformation will be measured Fig. 1.

A Dino-Lite microscope with the magnification range of 10X~220X, resolution of 5 Megapixels, and field of view up to $2\text{mm}\times 1.5\text{mm}$ (for 200X magnification) is used in this research. The stand of the microscope and the sliding ruler are made by 3D printing technology. For the indicator, different materials and different technologies, such as laser engraving, SIM Chips, and Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs) from different electronic devices, were tried; with the SIM Chips being identified as the most appropriate material as they have very sharp and straight lines, in the images taken by 200X magnification, resulting in higher precision in the image processing.

After having the sliding ruler installed on the specimen, images are captured in the required time periods with the maximum proper magnification, then the images can be analyzed with motion analysis software, image processing software, or self-made coding. However, considering that one of the features intended for this research would be to have an open-source solution, this stage was performed with an open-source, Python code.

After capturing the images, they are denoised then the indicator is identified and tracked in the subsequent images to assess its displacement in terms of pixels, using Python's OpenCV library.

To have self-calibrating images, the thickness of the lines at the SIM were also measured. For this, a surface scanner machine (Veeco Dektak 150) available at the Department of Electronics of the University of Minho, was used. With the $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ ratio (scale), the displacement can be determined.

3 Verification

With the objective of validating this method, a test setup was used to assess the trueness of the developed method according to ISO 5725 Standards [5–7]. The test was made on a calibration table having the developed measurement system against a traditional measurement sensor, micrometer with a precision of $1\mu\text{m}$.

The trueness of the developed method is assessed by comparing the reading from the installed micrometer and results from the images taken by the microscope.

Random displacements were applied to the sliding ruler and the readings from the micrometer were recorded at the same time as capturing images by microscope. Fig. 2.a shows the comparison of the results from two methods, while the error of the

developed method can be seen in Fig. 2.b. Fig. 2.b indicates that the maximum difference between two methods is about 3 microns; therefore, the error of the developed method is in the allowable range which is defined as $<3\mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 1. A detailed schematic of the developed measurement method

Fig. 2. Trueness assessment: a) Comparison of the readings from Micrometer and the developed method; b) error of the developed method

4 Conclusion

To conclude a cost-effective deformation measurement method was developed and verified in laboratory. The method allows the measurement of deformations,

specifically delayed deformations of the building materials, in the range of less than 1mm. Furthermore, the system was developed using open-source solutions in order to facilitate its dissemination within the academic and technical communities.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through Marie Skłodowska-Curie project SUBLime [Grant Agreement no. 955986]. This work was partly financed by FCT / MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB / 04029/2020.

References

1. James Ball R, Charles Allen G: Load-dependent deformation and shrinkage in hydraulic lime mortars. *Int J Sustain Eng* 3, pp. 40–46 (2010).
2. Vejmelková E, Keppert M, Keršner Z, Rovnaníková P, Černý R: Mechanical, fracture-mechanical, hydric, thermal, and durability properties of lime–metakaolin plasters for renovation of historical buildings. *Constr Build Mater* 31, pp. 22–28 (2012).
3. Idiart A, Bisschop J, Caballero A, Lura P: A numerical and experimental study of aggregate-induced shrinkage cracking in cementitious composites. *Cem Concr Res* 42, pp. 272–281 (2012).
4. Brooks JJ: Composite modelling of masonry deformation. *Mater Struct* 23, pp. 241–251 (1990).
5. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) (2019): ISO 5725-2: 2019: Accuracy (Trueness and Precision) of Measurement Methods and Results-Part 2: Basic Method for the Determination of Repeatability and Reproducibility of a Standard Measurement Method. International Organization for Standardization
6. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) (2020): ISO 5725-4: 2020 Accuracy (Trueness and Precision) of Measurement Methods and Results: Part 4: Basic Method for the Determination of the Trueness of a Standard Measurement Method. International Organization for Standardization
7. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) (1994): ISO 5725-1: 1994: Accuracy (Trueness and Precision) of Measurement Methods and Results-Part 1: General Principles and Definitions. International Organization for Standardization